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Numerical Modeling of a Lightweight Point Absorber for Wave-Powered Desalination

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Abstract

This paper presents Water Bros Desalination's (WBD) work in developing a compact wave-driven desalination system for coastal disaster response. To predict system loads and potable water production, accurate simulation of the Wave Energy Converter (WEC) is crucial. The paper outlines the numerical model setup using *WEC-Sim*, a standard tool for simulating WECs in the *MATLAB/SIMULINK* environment. By focusing on regular waves, the study models the buoy motion within the heave, surge, and pitch degrees of freedom. A standard *WEC-Sim* setup was used, yielding a linear model, which required preliminarily calculating the hydrodynamic coefficients in *NEMOH* Boundary Element Method (BEM) software. The *WEC-Sim* model of a similar wave-powered desalination system validated the modeling methods. The "Hydraulic and Electric Reverse Osmosis Wave Energy Converter" (HERO WEC), developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), was selected for this validation. The HERO WEC produces over 6 times more water than the WBD WEC for the same regular wave state. Further, the dynamic behavior of both desalination WECs appears to differ significantly in motion amplitude and frequency.

Keywords: Desalination; point absorber; *WEC-Sim*; *MATLAB/SIMULINK*, Boundary-Element-Method

1. Introduction

Climate change and population growth continue to stress global water supplies, thus calling for alternative water sources [1]. With 29% of the US population living in coastline counties, the US Department of Energy's (DOE) 2019 *Powering the Blue Economy* report identified small-scale distributed desalination systems to be a near-term

Nomenclature					
$\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}}, \ddot{\mathbf{x}}$	Buoy position, velocity and acceleration	\mathbf{F}_v	Damping force	η	Wave elevation
\mathbf{m}	Mass matrix of the buoy	\mathbf{F}_{me}	Morison-Element force	t, t_r	Simulation and ramp time
\mathbf{F}_{hydro}	Hydrodynamic forces	\mathbf{F}_B	Net buoyancy restoring force	\Re	Real part
\mathbf{F}_{PTO}	PTO force	\mathbf{F}_g	Gravitational force	ω	Radian frequency
\mathbf{F}_m	Mooring forces	$\mathbf{A}(\omega)$	Added mass matrix	θ	Wave direction
\mathbf{F}_{exc}	Excitation force	$\mathbf{B}(\omega)$	Radiation damping matrix	ϕ	Wave phase
\mathbf{F}_{md}	Mean drift force	\mathbf{K}_{hs}	Hydrostatic stiffness matrix	k	Wave number
\mathbf{F}_{rad}	Radiation force	R_f	Ramp function	T	Wave period
		H	Wave height	λ	Wave length

opportunity to provide potable water for coastal communities [2,3]. In May 2023, the DOE announced to invest \$9 million to advance desalination and water reuse technology [1].

Water Bros Desalination (WBD) is a small business developing a modular wave-powered desalination system that emerged from the DOE Waves to Water Prize in 2022. The current WBD prototype uses commercial Reverse Osmosis (RO) pumps for desalination, where the desalination unit is built atop the Wave-Energy Converter (WEC), as depicted in Figure 1.a. The WEC comprises the point absorber and power take-off (PTO), which converts wave energy into mechanical energy using a shaft, a spool, a restoring spring, and a cable. As the buoy responds to waves, cable unwinding induces shaft rotation, powering RO pumps. The desalination system connects two RO-pump units to the PTO via belt drives. Figure 1.b outlines a simplified block diagram of the WBD system for illustrative purposes.

This paper outlines the numerical model establishment for the WBD system, enabling load and potable water production predictions during deployment. We used *WEC-Sim*, a widely adopted tool which enables complex WEC simulations using *MATLAB/SIMULINK*. The WBD prototype was simulated in 2-dimensional regular waves, accounting for three degrees of freedom while disregarding drag and nonlinear hydrodynamic forces. The chosen reference model describes a similar wave-powered desalination system called HERO WEC, which was developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [5]. It served as a basis due to its similar setup and was utilized to contextualize the simulations. A comparison between the buoy dimensions of both WECs can be found in Figure 1.c. The paper encompasses three sections: modeling, results and discussion, and conclusions.

2. Modeling

This section covers the governing equations of the buoy movement, describes the relevant assumptions, and introduces the software required to solve the governing equations.

2.1. Equation of Motion

Newton's second law yields the equation of motion of the system in 6 degrees of freedom, resulting in three equations for translational motion and three equations for rotational motion around each spatial axis [6]:

$$\mathbf{m}\ddot{\mathbf{x}} = (\mathbf{F}_{hydro}(t) + \mathbf{F}_g) + \mathbf{F}_{PTO}(t) + \mathbf{F}_m(t) \quad (1)$$

with the translational and rotational 6×1 acceleration vector $\ddot{\mathbf{x}}$ of the device, the 6×6 mass matrix \mathbf{m} , the hydrodynamic forces $\mathbf{F}_{hydro}(t)$, the gravitational force \mathbf{F}_g , the PTO forces $\mathbf{F}_{PTO}(t)$ and the mooring forces $\mathbf{F}_m(t)$. The hydrodynamic forces can be calculated using experiments, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) [6], or the radiation-diffraction model [8], as it is used in *WEC-Sim*. It is based on the assumption of irrotational and incompressible fluid behavior, and small-amplitude time-harmonic motion induced by linear monochromatic waves [8].

Fig. 1. (a) CAD model of the current WBD prototype, (b) simplified block-diagram of the WBD WEC subsystems for RO (pink) and PTO (cyan), (c) comparison of the dimensions between the reference model HERO-WEC and the herein modeled WBD WEC

Using this concept, *WEC-Sim* calculates the dynamic response by solving (1) around the buoy's center of gravity given as [4]:

$$\mathbf{m}\ddot{\mathbf{x}} = (\mathbf{F}_{exc}(t) + \mathbf{F}_{md}(t) + \mathbf{F}_{rad}(t) + \mathbf{F}_v(t) + \mathbf{F}_{me}(t) + \mathbf{F}_B(t)) + \mathbf{F}_{PTO}(t) + \mathbf{F}_m(t) \quad (2)$$

with the components of $\mathbf{F}_{hydro}(t)$ in the brackets of (2), namely the wave excitation force $\mathbf{F}_{exc}(t)$, the mean drift force $\mathbf{F}_{md}(t)$, the radiation force $\mathbf{F}_{rad}(t)$, the damping force $\mathbf{F}_v(t)$, the Morison Element force $\mathbf{F}_{me}(t)$ and the net buoyancy restoring force $\mathbf{F}_B(t)$. Since *WEC-Sim* generally considers 6 degrees of freedom, each 6x1 force vector includes both, a force and a torque component per spatial axis. The gravitational force from (1) is included in the buoyancy restoring force. The current WBD *WEC-Sim* model is based on a simplification of (2) denoting as:

$$\mathbf{m}\ddot{\mathbf{x}} = (\mathbf{F}_{exc}(t) + \mathbf{F}_{rad}(t) + \mathbf{F}_B(t)) + \mathbf{F}_{PTO}(t) \quad (3)$$

The three hydrodynamic forces in the brackets of (3) can be described by four hydrodynamic coefficients: the excitation force coefficient $\mathbf{F}_{exc}(t)$, the added-mass matrix $\mathbf{A}(\omega)$, the radiation-damping matrix $\mathbf{B}(\omega)$, and the hydrostatic stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_{hs} , as described in [4]. The PTO force is calculated using a *SIMULINK Simscape* model describing the interaction between the PTO and the desalination system, as shown in Figure 2.d. Finally, the regular waves are defined as planar sinusoidal waves, for which the incident wave is defined as $\eta(x, y, t)$:

$$\eta(x, y, t) = \frac{H}{2} \cos(\omega t - k(x \cos(\theta) + y \sin(\theta)) + \phi) \quad (4)$$

with the wave height H , the wave number $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, wave length λ , wave direction θ and wave phase ϕ .

2.2. WEC-Sim model

The employed numerical *WEC-Sim* model operates in the *MATLAB/SIMULINK* environment, utilizing the *Simscape Multibody* solver. Its modular design incorporates *SIMULINK* blocks representing various WEC subsystems—buoy, sea ground, and PTO. The calculation of buoy dynamics according to (3) requires the knowledge of the hydrodynamic coefficients, which were evaluated using *NEMOH*, an open-source software which considers the discretized buoy geometry panels as illustrated in Figure 2.a. The calculated hydrodynamic coefficients are provided in the appendix for both HERO WEC and WBD WEC. Figure 2.b showcases the *WEC-Sim* model of the WBD WEC with its color-coded blocks; yellow represents the buoy, green describes the PTO-RO subsystem, brown describes the sea ground, and cyan and orange represent the heave, surge, and pitch degrees of freedom. The model draws inspiration from the HERO WEC's configuration. Figure 2.d. conceals the *Simscape* model behind the green block in Figure 2.b, dedicated to computing PTO force concerning buoy displacement, velocity, and acceleration. The RO model's empirical nature as to be seen in Figure 2.d stems from data fitting from WBD wave-tank and ocean deployment tests. A distinctive feature of the WBD WEC is the combination of the PTO mooring cable and a pulley as shown in Figure 1.b to increase the travel and facilitate installation. This configuration has been modelled using *Simscape* blocks as shown in Figure 2.d.

2.3. Simulation setup

The simulation was conducted for regular waves with 0.5 m height and a 7 s period. For the domain, a size of 6 m and a water depth of 5 m was chosen. The buoy weighs 76.6 kg with a center of gravity at $x = 17.4$, $y = -12.8$ and $z = -142.1$ mm. *WEC-Sim* ran with the 'ode45' solver and a ramp time of 200 s. The Open Source software *ParaView* was used for postprocessing and analysis, as shown in Figure 2.c.

Fig. 2. (a) discretized buoy hull mesh for using the BEM software *NEMOH*, (b) WBD *WEC-Sim* model, (c) *ParaView* visualization of the buoy for regular waves, (d) PTO-RO submodel in *Simscape*

3. Results and Discussion

The buoy dynamics was studied by comparing the WBD WEC and the HERO WEC in terms of heave, surge, pitch position and velocity, and heave position against wave elevation. Initial comparison without PTO, as showed in Figure 3.a and 3.b, revealed similar qualitative behavior: oscillations with phase differences at the 7-second wave period for all degrees of freedom. However, three notable differences emerged. The WBD WEC exhibited a high-frequency pitching overlaid with a lower frequency pitching, a higher pitching velocity amplitude of 20 deg/s versus 3 deg/s in HERO WEC, and a greater surge amplitude of 1.4 m vs 0.6 m in HERO WEC. These might origin from the HERO WEC's higher mass, inertia, and surface area. Both WECs closely tracked waves in heave position against wave elevation, maintaining a consistent offset. Comparison of Figures 3.c and 3.d showed the HERO WEC producing 400 mL of water in 40 seconds, while WBD yielded 60 mL. This results in a daily water production of 864 L versus 130 L; the difference might origin from the diverging system designs and dimensions, however it could also come from a modeling error in Figure 2.d, as the WBD models for the PTO and the RO-pumps haven't been verified for the given use-case yet. Another reason could be a HERO WEC Eigen-frequency closer to the wave frequency of 0.14 Hz, which would enable greater power capture. Divergence in heaving position motion between Figures 3.a/3.b and 3.c/3.d highlights the influence of the PTO-design and the RO-pump-design on system dynamics.

Fig. 3. Comparing heave, surge, and pitch for the physical quantities position and velocity as well the comparison between the wave elevation and the heaving motion position for (a) the HERO WEC and (b) for the WBD WEC for the case of no PTO; same comparison of physical quantities between (c) the HERO WEC and (d) the WBD WEC but for an existing PTO, additionally with a comparison of the water production

4. Conclusion

This paper introduced the *WEC-Sim* model for the WBD WEC, simulating three degrees of freedom under regular wave conditions. Validation was achieved by comparing with the HERO WEC as a reference model. Results indicated a substantial water production difference, with HERO outperforming WBD by over 6 times in a 40-second window under the same wave conditions. Dynamic behaviors notably varied in amplitude and frequency between the two desalination WECs. Future steps involve verifying the WBD *WEC-Sim* model using [6] and analyze the WBD WEC's power absorption. Additionally, a physics-based RO model akin to HERO's will be developed, as well as encompassing nonlinear forces and hydrodynamic drag. The overall goal is to analyze the system regarding potable water production, average loads, and peak loads, assess economic viability, and dimension the WEC for its future deployment.

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Appendix A. Hydrodynamic coefficients

The hydrodynamic coefficients were calculated with the BEM software *NEMOH*, and were then imported in a nondimensionalized form by another open-source software called *BEMIO* for the use in *WEC-Sim* [4]:

$$\overline{|\mathbf{F}_{exc}(\omega)|} = \frac{|\mathbf{F}_{exc}(\omega)|}{\rho g}, \quad \overline{\mathbf{A}(\omega)} = \frac{\mathbf{A}(\omega)}{\rho}, \quad \overline{\mathbf{B}(\omega)} = \frac{\mathbf{B}(\omega)}{\rho\omega}, \quad \overline{\mathbf{K}_{hs}} = \frac{\mathbf{K}_{hs}}{\rho g} \quad (5)$$

The linear restoring stiffness \mathbf{K}_{hs} is a 6 x 6 matrix independent of the excitation frequency:

Table 1. linear restoring stiffness \mathbf{K}_{hs} of the both WEC systems

HERO buoy						WBD buoy					
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	2.2	0	0	0	0	0	1.04	0	0.02	0
0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0.08	0	0
0	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0.02	0	0.09	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The nondimensionalized hydrodynamic coefficients, as defined in (5), are plotted in Figure 4.a – 4.f over a frequency range of (0, 10) radian/s for the relevant degrees of freedom heave, surge and pitch.

Fig. 4. Plot of the hydrodynamic coefficients, namely $\mathbf{A}(\omega)$, $\mathbf{B}(\omega)$ and $\mathbf{F}_{exc}(\omega)$ for the (a) HERO WEC and (b) WBD WEC

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